

DIRECTIONS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF FINANCING THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The analysis and conclusions on the directions of increasing the efficiency of financing the education system in our country

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KEY WORDS

Social reform, budget system, education system, education system financing

1.Introduction.

It is known that the reforms in the field of education are one of the integral and decisive directions of the ongoing socio-economic reforms in our country.

It should be noted that we need to logically complete our large-scale work in this area, in particular, our adopted national programs on education. To this end, the most important task of the relevant ministries and departments of the Government, as well as the entire education system, esteemed professors and teachers is to thoroughly educate the younger generation, to bring them up as physically and spiritually mature people.

2.Analysis and discussion of results.

The Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan has submitted another draft budget for citizens dedicated to the draft State Budget for 2022. In 2022, the state budget is projected to spend 105,503.2 billion soums on social spending, of which education will account for the largest share. It is currently planned that about half of the state budget expenditures will be directed to the social sphere or 44.5% of

the total expenditures to the education sector. There are 18,345 preschools in the country by 2021, and by 2022 it is planned to reconstruct and overhaul 22,429 preschools and build new preschools. The goal is to expand the involvement of children in preschool education and to educate the next generation.

In 2022, 30,823.4 million soums will be allocated to finance general education and out-of-school institutions. UZS or general secondary education expenditures are projected to increase by 1.18 times.

Extracurricular activities include children's music and art schools and Barkamol Avlod schools. It is planned to allocate 640.8 billion soums from the state budget for the maintenance of children's music and art schools, as well as 251.1 million soums from the state budget for the maintenance of Barkamol Avlod schools.

The main indicators and expenditures for secondary special vocational education in 2022 will be 802, and the state budget is planned to spend 2 222.5 billion soums. It is also planned to allocate 326.2 billion soums from the state budget for academic

lyceums in 2022. In 2022, 497.6 billion soums will be allocated from the state budget for vocational colleges, 1,130.3 billion soums from the state budget for vocational schools, 203.0 billion soums from the state budget for technical colleges, and retraining in the construction industry. We can see that training centers will cost 65.4 billion soums.

It is obvious that in the future the number of vocational and academic lyceums will

decrease, and the state budget will reduce spending.

From the State Budget in 2022 to finance the higher education system

It is planned to direct 5,448.8 billion soums.

3. Conclusions and suggestions.

In conclusion, the effective organization of the financing of the education system is an example of the correct distribution of the state budget, as well as the control over public spending by budget organizations.

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